

AGIS-like solution for the sky-like astrometric data in Radiation Campaign #4

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Abstract

This note describes an AGIS-like (purely geometric) analysis of the sky-like astrometric data of the Radiation Campaign #4 data. Following the principles in Lindegren (LL-082) and Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086), but using a more efficient and flexible solution method, and thanks to the improved AC sampling in RC#4, the positional bias is mapped out with good confidence as function of magnitude and time since charge injection, and an improved estimate of the excess noise in the damaged region of the CCD is derived.

Document History

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1 Introduction

Following the analysis of astrometric sky-like test data in Radiation Campaign #3, reported in Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086), it was concluded that a better sampling of the AC positions of the mask and of a broad range of times since charge injection were needed for a proper determination and analysis of the CTI effects. This led to the specifications in Crowley & Lindegren (CMC-001) for the Radiation Campaign #4 tests. In this context a new idea took form, namely to introduce the Charge Distortion Model (CDM; Short, AS-015) into the analysis, thus simulating in a sense not only the AGIS-like solution, but also the preceding stages of CDM and LSF calibrations and the image parameter determination (IPD) via these models, all of which are part of the CCD data pre-processing in IDT and IDU.

Details of the idea were subsequently fixed during a working meeting at ESTEC on 6 October 2010. As presented at the 7th meeting of the Radiation Task Force (Barcelona, 18–19 October 2010) the planned activities are as shown in Fig. 1. The initial IPD will use the default (mean, symmetric) LSF model H_0 for the centroiding, which implies that considerable positional biases are introduced in the irradiated part of the CCD. The following AGIS-like solution (called AGIS0 in the flow chart) will be able to estimate this bias as function of magnitude and time since charge injection. Comparing the undamaged image profiles with the damaged (and shifted) ones, allows one to make initial calibrations of the LSF and CDM. These models will result in new (and hopefully improved) image parameters, which will be input to a new AGIS-like solution (AGIS1). If the CDM works, the new solution should give smaller bias as function of magnitude and time since charge injection. Iterating the LSF/CDM calibration and AGIS-like solution should ideally eliminate the bias completely.

It is expected that this analysis will provide an additional, and possibly more stringent test of the current CDM model, as well as useful experience on the CDM calibration and the feasibility or possible weaknesses of the current baseline approach for the CTI mitigation in DPAC.

The present note describes the initial AGIS-like solution (AGIS1 in Fig. 1) before any mitigation is attempted by means of the CDM model. Apart from being an important step in the envisaged analysis scheme, it provides a new, and sharper, limit on the astrometric degradation of the mission due to radiation damage, replacing the one derived in Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086). This limit applies to the worst-case scenario that the DPAC mitigation scheme is unsuccessful, so that the CTI bias must be determined entirely as part of the geometric calibration in AGIS.

2 Overview of the data

The Radiation Campaign #4 (RC#4) astrometric sky-like test data (second run) were delivered by Astrium in January 2011 (EADS Astrium, GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00590). They were pre-processed by C. Crowley in a similar manner as the RC#3 data described in Lindegren & Crow-

FIGURE 1: Flow chart for the analysis of the astrometric sky-like test data simulating the outer iterations between AGIS and the calibration of CDM and LSF in IDU.

ley (LL-086), and the image parameters (location and flux) were determined by a maximum-likelihood fit of the calibrated LSF model to the sample values. This image parameter determination (IPD) provided the basic input to the AGIS-like analysis; thus, for every observation we know the AL location of the image centre (u), the formal error of the location (σ_u), and the G magnitude, as well as the corresponding indices of the star (i), dataset (j), and run (k), the AC coordinate m of the sample window, and the time T , in TDI periods, since the previous charge injection (CI).

The RC#4 data analysed here consist of 16 datasets, for eight different AC positions of the mask (Fig. 2) and the two orientations of the mask ('up' and 'down'). Each dataset consists of 900 runs, with 300 different delays (T) from the CI to the first star, in steps of 10 TDI periods (pixels): $T = 10, 20, 30, \dots, 3000$. For each delay there are three consecutive runs with a random sub-pixel phasing. Although the plan had been to have a periodic CI repeating every 3000 TDI periods (approximately equal to the length of the star pattern in the AL direction), there was in fact only one CI per run, preceding the star images as described above; as a result, the stars at the trailing end of the mask had T in the range from about 3000 TDI periods to 6000 TDI periods and were never observed soon after a CI. The impact of this oversight is briefly discussed in Sect. 5.

The two datasets obtained in mask position 1 (Fig. 2) were found to contain corrupt data and were not used in the analysis, which therefore consists of 14 datasets in 7 different AC positions. Moreover, two consecutive runs ($k = 305$ and 306) in one of the datasets ($j = 10$) were also found to be corrupt and therefore not used in the analysis. The input data consisted of 12 598

FIGURE 2: The eight different AC positions of the sky-like mask relative to the non-irradiated and irradiated areas of the CCD.

runs in total.

For reasons outlined in Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086), most of the stars in the regular part of the mask were not used in the analysis. The 852 stars used are the same as Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086) and their layout on the mask is shown in Fig. 3.

A few ‘bad columns’ were identified and the corresponding observations were rejected *a priori*. This affected column numbers $m = 132$ (hot column) and $420 \leq m \leq 428$ (the transition region from the non-irradiated area, $m < 420$, to the fully irradiated area, $m > 428$). The total number of observations input to the analysis was 10 687 315.

For the subsequent analysis it was found convenient to re-label the actually used stars, datasets, and runs by consecutive numbers. Thus, the 852 stars actually used in the analysis were indexed $i = 1 \dots 852$, and the 14 retained datasets were indexed $j = 1 \dots 14$. For the individual runs, a single sequence of $k = 1 \dots 12598$ was used rather than starting at $k = 1$ for each new dataset. Thus j is implicitly defined by k , and every observation is uniquely defined by a combination of indices i and k . From here on, all indices referred to in the text, equations and figures are these re-labelled ones. Lookup tables are kept which allow them to be translated to the original indices when needed.

FIGURE 3: A plot of the (x_i, y_i) coordinates for the 853 stars (i.e., holes) used in the present AGIS-like solutions. In addition to the 813 stars in the sky-like area, 40 stars from the outer regular part of the mask were included.

3 Generic reduction model

The generic model fitted to the data is very similar to what is described in Lindegren (LL-082) and Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086), however with some differences to be discussed below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{ik} - s_j x_i &= s_j \Delta x_i^{(0)} + \left[\Delta x_i^{(1)} \right] \\
 &+ a_k^{(00)} + a_k^{(10)} \times \left(\frac{x_i}{x_{\max}} \right) + a_k^{(01)} \times \left(\frac{y_i}{y_{\max}} \right) \\
 &+ \sum_{\alpha \geq 0} \sum_{\beta \geq 0} c_j^{(\alpha\beta)} \times P_\alpha \left(\frac{s_j x_i}{x_{\max}} \right) \times P_\beta \left(\frac{s_j y_i}{y_{\max}} \right) \\
 &\quad 2 \leq \alpha + \beta \leq D_c \\
 &+ \sum_{\alpha=0}^{D_d} d_s^{(\alpha)} \times \left(\frac{m_{ik} - m}{125} \right)^\alpha \\
 &+ \sum_{\alpha \geq 0} \sum_{\beta \geq 0} b_r^{(\alpha\beta)} \times \left(\frac{G_i - 15}{5} \right)^\alpha \times (\log_{10} T_{ik} - 2.5)^\beta. \tag{1} \\
 &\quad 0 \leq \alpha + \beta \leq D_b
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, u_{ik} is the observed location of the image of star i in run k , x_i is the nominal position of star i on the mask (derived from Sect. 5.1 in EADS Astrium (GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00590)) and $s_j = \pm 1$ depending on the mask position in dataset j . $P_n(x)$ denotes the Legendre polynomial of degree n . The unknowns on the right-hand side are:

- $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$ is the correction to the nominal AL position of star i on the mask;
- $a_k^{(\alpha\beta)}$ are the local ‘attitude’ parameters in run k , representing the AL origin of the run ($\alpha\beta = 00$), the AL scale error ($\alpha\beta = 10$), and the mask rotation ($\alpha\beta = 01$);
- $c_j^{(\alpha\beta)}$ are ‘large-scale calibration’ parameters in dataset j representing optical and other distortions that may vary between datasets but are assumed to be constant within the dataset. The terms of degree $\alpha + \beta \leq 1$ are not included here because they are covered by the attitude parameters;
- $d_s^{(\alpha)}$ are the AL offset ($\alpha = 0$) and slope ($\alpha = 1$) of stitching block s , relative to its central AC position m_s . Although the formulation allows quadratic and higher-order polynomials to the arbitrary degree D_d , in practice only $D_d = 0$ or 1 have been used;
- $b_r^{(\alpha\beta)}$ are parameters of the bias model for CCD region r ($r = 1$ for the undamaged and $r = 2$ for the damaged region), depending on the powers α and β of the magnitude of the star, G_i , and the time since change injection, $\log T_{ik}$, respectively.

The bracketed term on the right-hand side, $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$, is only used in ‘Model B’. It represents a systematic shift of each star in the AL direction, independent of the mask orientation; this is interpreted as an effect of the optical distortion in the optical set-up (Sect. B). ‘Model A’ consists of all the terms in Eq. (1) except the bracketed one.

It can be noted that the functional dependencies of all the terms have been scaled in such a way that the parameter values are representative for the corresponding AL shifts (in TDI periods): for the terms using Legendre polynomials they are roughly equal to the RMS shift, while for the others they approximately correspond to the shift at the edges of the considered range. For example, the stitching slope parameter $d_s^{(1)}$ gives the AL image shift at the edge of the stitching block, due to the slope (since the blocks are 250 pixels wide). Thus, the relative importance of the different parameters can be directly judged from their sizes.

The most important differences of the above model from the one used in RC#3 (described in Lindegren & Crowley, LL-086) are as follows:

- The parameters $a_k^{(10)}$ representing the AL scale error and $a_k^{(01)}$ representing the orientation error of the mask have been introduced as independent parameters for each

run (k). Including the rotation parameter in this way was planned already in Lindgren (LL-082) but was later abandoned because it gave a normal equations system that is too large to be handled conveniently in MATLAB. With the new solution method (Appendix A) this is no longer a limitation, and there is clearly a real variation of the AL scale from one run to the next, and probably also of the mask orientation (see Sect. 4.1).

- The maximum degree of the ‘large scale calibration’ polynomial is no longer fixed to 3 but can be an arbitrary degree D_c . The required degree depends on how stable the setup is between the datasets. This has not been systematically investigated, and it was simply assumed that the inclusion of cubic terms is sufficient.
- The stitching slope parameter $d_s^{(1)}$ is scaled to the size of the effect at the edges of the stitching block through the introduction of the factor $1/125$ in the corresponding function (125 is half the block width in AC pixels).
- The bias term is written as an arbitrary polynomial of degree D_b in G and $\log_{10} T$.

The solution method also includes several improvements, including a more consistent handling of outliers (Appendix A.3).

4 Results

A large number of solutions have been made, using different numbers of attitude, calibration and bias terms, and for both Model A (i.e., without the ‘star error’ terms $\Delta_i^{(1)}$) and Model B (including the ‘star error’ terms). While the RMS size of the residuals, as measured by the unit weight error U in Eq. (9), varies a great deal between the solutions, they are remarkably stable when it comes to the interpretation of the positional bias as function of G and T . This suggests that the bias effect is well decoupled from other geometrical factors such as the ‘attitude’ of the mask or stitching errors. As a consequence we are only presenting a few representative solutions here in order to illustrate some important features.

Table 2 is an overview of the four solutions to be discussed below. Solutions A-0, A-5 and A-10 use Model A, while B-5 uses Model B. The only difference between A-5 and B-5 is the inclusion of the bracketed term in Eq. (1) in solution B-5. The number in these designations (0, 5 and 10) is the number of bias terms (per region) included. For A-0, no bias term is included. For A-5 and B-5, the bias terms included are $(\alpha\beta) = (00), (01), (10), (20),$ and (30) , that is:

$$\dots + b_r^{(00)} + b_r^{(01)}t + b_r^{(10)}g + b_r^{(20)}g^2 + b_r^{(30)}g^3 + \dots \quad (2)$$

for $r = 1$ (undamaged region) and $r = 2$ (damaged region), where $g = (G - 15)/5$ and $t = \log_{10} T - 2.5$. The only significance of this particular selection of terms is that it was used for the analysis in Lindgren & Crowley (LL-086). For solution A-10, all 10 terms up to degree $D_b = 4$ were included.

TABLE 2: Main characteristics of the various solutions discussed in the text. Solution A-0, A-5 and A-10 are for Model A using different numbers of bias terms, while solution B-5 is for Model B using the same bias terms as A-5.

Input data				
Number of datasets, J	14			
Number of runs, K	12 598			
Number of stars, I	852			
Number of accepted observations, N	10 687 315			
Number of rejected observations in the K runs	46 181 (0.43%)			
Solution	A-0	A-5	A-10	B-5
Number of local parameters (a_k)	37 794	37 794	37 794	37 794
Number of global parameters	955	965	975	1 817
of which star parameters (Δx_i)	852	852	852	1 704
large-scale calibration parameters (c_j)	98	98	98	98
small-scale calibration parameters (d_s)	5	5	5	5
bias parameters (b_r)	0	10	20	10
Total number of parameters	38 749	38 757	38 769	39 609
Rank defect (number of constraints)	11	12	12	25
Degrees of freedom	10 481 058	10 481 049	10 481 039	10 480 210
Unit weight error, U	1.743786	1.515563	1.496277	1.077661
Average downweighting factor, $\langle h_{ik} \rangle$	0.984091	0.984233	0.984244	0.984268
Excess noise for $16 \leq G \leq 18$ [TDI]	(*)	0.00713	0.00686	0.00687
Excess noise for $16 \leq G \leq 18$ [μas]	(*)	420	404	405
Figures	7, 13	4, 5, 8, 12–20	9, 12, 13	11–20

(*) The excess noise could not be reliably determined for $G < 18.5$ in Solution A-0.

4.1 Scale and rotation errors

All three attitude terms $a_k^{(00)}$ (shift), $a_k^{(10)}$ (scale error), and $a_k^{(01)}$ (rotation) were used in these solutions. Trial solutions in which the scale and/or rotation parameters were excluded gave somewhat higher U values without greatly affecting the other parameters. The scale errors vary quite significantly from one run to the next (which means that it cannot be included among the calibration parameters, which are constant within a dataset), and the same is probably true for the rotation errors. The scale errors, at least, exhibit a very clear periodic variation as exemplified in Fig. 4. This is seen equally strong throughout all the data, with typically 20 cycles per dataset. According to (EADS Astrium, GAIA.ASF.TCN.PLM.00590) the average time for the acquisition of a dataset is about 803 min, so the observed period corresponds to 40 min in real time. A likely cause of the effect is temperature variations, a hypothesis that was verified by examining the temperature logging files. For example, Fig. 6 shows the (smoothed) intercon-

FIGURE 4: Variation of the AL scale error $a_k^{(10)}$ with run number (k) for the first 1200 runs (top) and for runs 9000 through 10200 (bottom). Since the datasets consist of 900 runs each, the top diagram shows the first (accepted) dataset and the beginning of the second set, while the bottom diagram shows the 11th dataset and the beginning of the 12th. Results are for Solution A-5. See text for a discussion of the periodicity.

tion board temperature for the dataset corresponding to $k = 8999$ through 9898. Clearly these temperature measurements have a periodic component with a period around 40 min, which is anti-correlated with the scale errors.¹ The discontinuity seen at $k = 9736$ in the bottom diagram

¹The PEM temperature measurements, also at room temperature, shows very similar variations, while the CCD support measurements, at about 162.5 K, are not obviously following the same pattern.

FIGURE 5: Variation of the rotation parameter $a_k^{(01)}$ with run number (k) for the first 1200 runs (top) and for runs 9000 through 10200 (bottom). Results are for Solution A-5.

of Fig. 4 was apparently caused by a time gap of 23 min, or about half a temperature cycle, that occurred about 665 min into the dataset.

FIGURE 6: Measured temperature at the interconnection board during the acquisition of the 12th dataset (corresponding to the first 900 runs in the lower diagrams in Figs. 4 and 5. Note the acquisition gap which produced the discontinuity in Fig. 4. Temperature data have been smoothed with a kernel 7 points wide. (Diagram by courtesy of C. Crowley.)

4.2 Bias results for Model A

In this section we present the results of solutions A-0, A-5 and A-10 concerning the bias terms and related statistics. Appendix C gives additional results and residual plots for other parameters, but only for solution A-5.

Figures 7–9 show the bias for solutions A-0, A-5 and A-10, respectively, as function of G and $\log_{10} T$. The top diagrams show the fitted bias functions, which are two-dimensional polynomials with 0, 5, and 10 terms, respectively (thus the fitted bias is identically zero in A-0). Looking at solutions A-5 and A-10, it is seen that, as expected, the fitted bias is generally smaller in the undamaged region than in the damaged region, and that it generally increases with T . However, the fitted polynomials obviously behave rather erratically, especially in A-10, and the validity of the fits can be questioned.

To examine the quality of the fits, the residuals were examined in the $(G, \log_{10} T)$ plane. The plane was divided into pixels of size $0.5 \text{ mag} \times 0.2 \text{ dex}$, and the mean residual was computed in each pixel, using a robust procedure. The number of observations available per pixel is shown in Fig. 10. The resulting mean residuals, displayed in the middle diagrams of Figs. 7–9, are quite significant in many pixels, and a better estimate of true bias might be obtained by adding the mean residual to the value of the fitted bias function in each pixel. The result of this operation is

shown in the bottom diagrams. Here a remarkably consistent picture emerges of $b(G, \log_{10} T)$ both in the undamaged and damaged regions:

- In the undamaged region, the bias is relatively flat (typically within ± 0.01 TDI periods) for $T \gtrsim 150$ TDI periods, while for smaller T it becomes increasingly negative. It is possible that this is not a CTI effect but related to the background slope in the trail of the CI. There is no clear dependence on G .
- In the damaged region a similar, but smaller effect is seen for $T \lesssim 150$ TDI periods. For larger T , up to about 1500 TDI periods, the bias increases smoothly, but still without any clear dependence on G .
- In the damaged region for $T \gtrsim 1500$ TDI periods, the bias has a maximum around $G \simeq 15.2$ mag and possibly a broad minimum for $18 \lesssim G \lesssim 19.5$ before increasing again for the faintest stars.
- In the damaged region for the faintest stars ($G > 20$) and smallest CI delays ($\log_{10} T < 1.2$) there is a strong positive bias of unknown origin.

When interpreting the diagrams, it should be remembered that the bias functions are undefined with respect to an offset, which is the same in both regions but could differ between solutions. For example, between the bottom diagrams in Figs. 8 and 9 there is slight difference in offset which makes a comparison somewhat harder. Also, the distinction between positive and negative biases is in principle arbitrary.

FIGURE 7: Bias estimation in solution A-0 for the undamaged region (left) and damaged region (right column). The top diagrams show the fitted bias function (which in this solution is zero, as no bias terms were fitted), the middle diagrams show the mean residual from the fit, and the bottom diagrams show the sum of the fitted bias function and the mean residual. The black pixels have no data.

FIGURE 8: Bias estimation in solution A-5 for the undamaged region (left) and damaged region (right column). The top diagrams show the fitted bias function (a polynomial in G and $\log_{10} T$ with 5 terms), the middle diagrams show the mean residual from the fit, and the bottom diagrams show the sum of the fitted bias function and the mean residual. The black pixels have no data.

FIGURE 9: Bias estimation in solution A-10 for the undamaged region (left) and damaged region (right column). The top diagrams show the fitted bias function (a complete 4th degree polynomial in G and $\log_{10} T$ with 10 terms), the middle diagrams show the mean residual from the fit, and the bottom diagrams show the sum of the fitted bias function and the mean residual. The black pixels have no data.

FIGURE 10: Number of observations per pixel used to compute the mean residuals. These diagrams are virtually identical for all solutions. The excess numbers for $G = 15-16.5$ and $\log_{10} T \simeq 1.7$ are due to the 40 stars from the regular mask (see Fig. 3) for which the ‘self-injection’ is counted as $T = 50$ TDI periods.

4.3 Bias results for Model B

In this section we present bias results for solution B-5, while Appendix C gives additional results and residual plots for other parameters.

Figure 11 shows the bias for solution B-5 in the same manner as for the Model A solutions in Sect. 4.2. In spite of the fact that some of the bias must have been absorbed by the ‘star error’ parameters $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$, the results are remarkably similar to the ones for Model A. The same trends are observed, except that the negative biases for small T seen for Model A seems to have disappeared. (This seems to contradict the earlier explanation in terms of the sloping background.) The amplitude of the total effect is somewhat smaller than for Model A, which is expected if some of the bias is absorbed by the star error parameters.

4.4 Comparison of the bias estimates from the different solutions

As previously remarked, the comparison of different solutions is somewhat obscured by the floating zero point (offset) of the bias terms. In order to eliminate this uncertainty, we show in Fig. 12 a comparison of the total biases in solutions A5, A-10 and B-5, where the offsets have been (arbitrarily) adjusted to give $\langle b(G, \log_{10} T) \rangle = 0$ in the area $17 \leq G \leq 19$ mag and $2.4 \leq \log_{10} T \leq 2.6$. The almost identical results in A-5 and A-10 are shown even more clearly here, as well as the similarities and differences between the A and B solutions. Although the estimates based on solution B-5 have a generally smoother and nicer look, the estimations based on A-5 are probably more reliable, at least concerning the total amplitude of the bias effect.

4.5 Excess noise in the damaged region

The excess noise in the damaged region was estimated in a slightly different way than in Lindgren & Crowley (LL-086). For every star that had accepted observations in both regions, the sample variance of the residuals was computed separately for the two regions, and the difference taken. Although the difference is positive for most stars, it is quite often negative as well (meaning that the variance was smaller in the damaged region). In Fig. 13 the red points show the estimated excess noise for the stars with a positive difference (i.e., the red points are the square-root of the excess variance, plotted against the magnitude of those stars). For the stars with a negative difference, the blue points show the square-root of the absolute value of the difference.

In order to estimate the excess noise as function of G , all the differences (whether positive or negative) were sorted according to magnitude, and a 35-point running median was calculated. The thick black curves in Fig. 13 show the square-root of the median difference (whenever the median is positive); this constitutes a reasonable and robust estimate of the excess noise as function of G . The thin black curve is the nominal standard error of the AL location estimator

taken from de Bruijne (JDB-053).

The resulting estimates of the excess noise are rather similar in all solutions, and suggest a plateau at around 0.007 TDI periods (about 400 μas) for $G \lesssim 18$ mag. For fainter stars the excess noise is a roughly constant fraction (about 40%) of the nominal standard error at that magnitude.

The more precise estimates of the excess noise in Table 2 were calculated from the median difference in variance for stars with G between 16 and 18 mag.

5 Conclusions

The RC#4 data are of very good quality and the AGIS-like solution allows to map the bias (image shift) reliably as a function of magnitude (G) and time since charge injection (T), both in the damaged and undamaged region, albeit with insufficient sampling for some important combinations of G and T (see below). The top maps in Fig. 12 summarize the most reliable estimates of the total biases. A remarkable feature in these maps is the very weak magnitude dependence, except for the longest CI delays ($T \gtrsim 1000$ TDI periods). This is in stark contrast to the strong magnitude dependence found in the corresponding analysis of the RC#3 data (Lindgren & Crowley, LL-086). Since different CCDs were used in the two campaigns, a possible conclusion is that the bias behaviour can vary substantially between devices. This could be related to the functioning (or non-functioning) of the SBC.

The excess noise in the damaged region, due to unmodelled bias effects, is $\simeq 400 \mu\text{as}$ for $G \lesssim 18$ mag, or 30% smaller than in the corresponding analysis of the RC#3 data (Lindgren & Crowley, LL-086). Note that no provision was made for the ‘pollution’ effect in this analysis.

A new algorithm for solving the large system of normal equations has been developed and used in the present analysis, see Appendix A. It allows to introduce many more unknowns, e.g., representing large-scale variations from one run to the next. It is found that at least the scale and rotation of the mask vary significantly between runs, in a quasi-periodic manner which seems to be correlated with temperature variations.

A possible physical explanation has been found for the so-called ‘star effect’ in terms of the optical distortions of the mask-projection system, see Appendix B.

Due to an oversight in the scheduling of the CI, the RC#4 data suffer from a poor sampling at small T values, especially for the bright magnitudes. This means that the bias function cannot be mapped with these data over the whole intended range of (G, T) values. A complementary set of test data has therefore been requested as part of RC#5 (EADS Astrium, GAIA.ASF.PLN.PLM.00097), to be analysed together with the present data set.

FIGURE 11: Bias estimation in solution B-5 for the undamaged region (left) and damaged region (right column). The top diagrams show the fitted bias function (a polynomial in G and $\log_{10} T$ with 5 terms), the middle diagrams show the mean residual from the fit, and the bottom diagrams show the sum of the fitted bias function and the mean residual. The black pixels have no data.

FIGURE 12: Comparison of the total bias estimation (fitted + mean residual) for solutions A-5 (top), A-10 (middle) and B-5 (bottom). For these diagrams, the bias offset has been arbitrarily fixed by requiring $b(G, \log_{10} T) \simeq 0$ at the centre of each map (see text for the precise condition).

FIGURE 13: Estimation of the excess noise in the damaged region relative to the undamaged region. The four diagrams are for solutions A-0 (top left) and A-5 (top right), A-10 (bottom left), and B-5 (bottom right). The thick black curves show a running median of the estimated excess noise (see text for further explanation). The thin black curve the $\sigma(G)$ relation in AF according to de Bruijne (JDB-053).

A Appendix: Successive elimination of attitude parameters

A.1 Background

In the generic reduction model of Eq. (1), the attitude parameters $a_k^{(0)}$ and $a_k^{(1)}$ make up the largest share of the model parameters. For example, in a typical reduction of the RC#4 test data there are 37 794 attitude parameters (i.e., 3 per run), while all the other parameters together only number about 1000. In the least squares solution of all the parameters, the normal equation matrix is a square, symmetric matrix of the same dimension as the total number of parameters, or nearly 40 000 in this case. Handling matrices of this size in MATLAB is entirely feasible, but the execution times for solving the system tend to become excessive and it is even worse if we want to make a singular value decomposition (SVD). Moreover, the solution needs to be iterated some 10 times to provide a robust result by eliminating or downweighting of outliers.

However, the design equations are very sparse, and in fact have the well-known ‘block angular’ (Björck, 1996) form very often encountered in geodetic, astrometric, and many other problems – indeed, the astrometric core solution for Gaia is basically of this form (Bombrun et al., 2010). This form results when every observation depends on only two categories of parameters (or unknowns): a small number of ‘local’ parameters, that are common only to a limited subset of the observations, and ‘global’ parameters, that are common to all observations.² In our case a convenient division is to regard the attitude parameters $a_k^{(0)}$ and $a_k^{(1)}$ as local ones, as these two parameters appear in the equations for all the observations in run k , but not in any other observations; all the other parameters are then regarded as global (even though not all of them apply to every observation).

Not surprisingly, methods to deal efficiently with block angular least-squares problem are well known and described for example in Björck (1996). For the present purpose we will adopt the very simple strategy of looping through the observations and accumulating the normal equations, while successively eliminating the local parameters after each run has been processed. When all the runs have been processed, we are left with a system of equations for the global parameters, which is readily solved. Usually, this would have been followed by a back-substitution of the global parameters into the equations for each run in order to solve the local parameters, but that is not required if we are anyway iterating the least-squares solution in order to eliminate outliers. The corresponding updates of the local parameters can then just as well be done in the next iteration, while eliminating the local parameters. The updating of the local parameters is therefore lagging behind the global parameters by one iteration, but that makes no difference once the iterations have converged.³

²The division into local and global parameters is somewhat arbitrary, and may depend on how the problem is structured. Crucially, however, you arrive in the end at exactly the same solution – at least mathematically speaking – independent of the chosen division, namely, the same as if the full problem was treated directly. However, the amount of storage and computation needed for the solution can vary hugely depending on the division.

³It is important to note that this is *not* an iterative solution method for the linear system of equations, as is

A.2 Solution method

Mathematically, the observation equations in Eq. (1) for K runs can be written in block angular form as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_1 & & & \mathbf{B}_1 \\ & \mathbf{A}_2 & & \mathbf{B}_2 \\ & & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & & \mathbf{A}_K & \mathbf{B}_K \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_1 \\ \mathbf{a}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{a}_K \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{r}_1 \\ \mathbf{r}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{r}_K \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{a}_k contain the local (attitude) parameters and \mathbf{b} the global (all remaining) parameters. \mathbf{r}_k is the vector of residuals in run k . With $N_a = 2$ attitude parameters per run, $N_g \sim 10^3$ global parameters, and N_s stars, and assuming that each run contains one observation per star, the dimensions of the various sub-matrices and vectors are:

$$\mathbf{A}_k : N_s \times N_a, \quad \mathbf{B}_k : N_s \times N_b, \quad \mathbf{r}_k : N_s \times 1, \quad \mathbf{a}_k : N_a \times 1, \quad \mathbf{b} : N_b \times 1. \quad (4)$$

Subsequently we shall assume that each observation equation has unit weight, so that its expected noise has unit variance. This is not true as the equations are given above, but the introduction of the weight of each observation, w_{ik} , is an almost trivial modification of the equations to be discussed later.

The normal equations are obtained by pre-multiplying Eq. (3) by the transpose of the block-angular matrix; the result is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}'_1 \mathbf{A}_1 & & & \mathbf{A}'_1 \mathbf{B}_1 \\ & \mathbf{A}'_2 \mathbf{A}_2 & & \mathbf{A}'_2 \mathbf{B}_2 \\ & & \ddots & \vdots \\ & & & \mathbf{A}'_K \mathbf{A}_K & \mathbf{A}'_K \mathbf{B}_K \\ \mathbf{B}'_1 \mathbf{A}_1 & \mathbf{B}'_2 \mathbf{A}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{B}'_K \mathbf{A}_K & \sum_k \mathbf{B}'_k \mathbf{B}_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{a}_1 \\ \mathbf{a}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{a}_K \\ \mathbf{b} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}'_1 \mathbf{r}_1 \\ \mathbf{A}'_2 \mathbf{r}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{A}'_K \mathbf{r}_K \\ \sum_k \mathbf{B}'_k \mathbf{r}_k \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The diagonal blocks $\mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{A}_k$ are of size $N_a \times N_a$ and can be trivially inverted (the block is positive definite if the run contains at least two stars with different y_i). This allows to write the local updates in run k in terms of the global updates \mathbf{b} :

$$\mathbf{a}_k = (\mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{A}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_k (\mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{b}), \quad k = 1 \dots K. \quad (6)$$

Substituting these in the last block row of Eq. (5) gives a system of equations which now contains only the global unknowns:

$$\sum_k \left(\mathbf{B}'_k \mathbf{B}_k - \mathbf{B}'_k \mathbf{A}_k (\mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{A}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{B}_k \right) \mathbf{b} = \sum_k \mathbf{B}'_k \left(\mathbf{r}_k - \mathbf{A}_k (\mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{A}_k)^{-1} \mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{r}_k \right), \quad (7)$$

basically the case for AGIS: iterations are here only needed to identify and downweight outliers. If downweighting is not used, the described procedure gives the exact solution for the global parameters already in the first iteration, and for the local parameters in the second; all subsequent updates are strictly zero.

or $F\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{f}$ for brevity. This system is of dimension $N_g \sim 10^3$ and therefore easily solved. It is, however, in general singular, because of the degeneracy between certain combinations of the parameters (see Lindegren, LL-082, for details). In the analysis of the RC#3 data, the degeneracies were overcome by introducing constraints, as described in Lindegren (LL-082). It is not so easy to derive the constraints that just allows the system to be solved without forcing the results, and it also makes the code difficult to maintain, since any modification of the reduction model may require additional constraints. In the present method, thanks to the modest size of the matrix in Eq. (7), we can however dispense with the constraints altogether by using a singular value decomposition (SVD) of the matrix and calculating the pseudo-solution of the equations. Among all the solution vectors \mathbf{b} satisfying Eq. (7), the pseudo-solution has minimum Euclidean norm $\|\mathbf{b}\|$.

The accumulation of the reduced normal equations in Eq. (7) is conveniently organized in two nested loops, an outer loop over the runs (k) and an inner loop over the observations in the run (here distinguished by the star index i). Introducing $\mathbf{C}_k = \mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{A}_k$, $\mathbf{D}_k = \mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{B}_k$, and $\mathbf{e}_k = \mathbf{A}'_k \mathbf{r}_k$ we have the pseudo-code in Algorithm 1. The local coefficient array \mathbf{p} in line 5 is a row matrix containing the coefficients of the local parameters in Eq. (1), i.e., $\mathbf{p} = (1, y_i/y_{\max})$, and similarly \mathbf{q} is a row matrix of length N_g containing the coefficients of the global parameters (most of the coefficients are zero).

Note how the observation weight w is introduced in lines 6 and 7. Formally, the weight of the observation ik is given by the inverse square of its standard error, $w_{ik} = \sigma_{ik}^{-2}$. However, for outliers the weight is further decreased by the downweighting factor (Sect. A.3). As previously explained, the algorithm must be executed at least twice in order to determine the local parameters correctly, as their updating lags behind that of the global parameters. However, in practice more iterations are needed before the downweighting factors have settled. Thus, although the solution method described above is a *direct* solution of the normal equations (as opposed to an iterative solution method such as used in AGIS), it must still be iterated in order to handle the outliers. However, the required number of iterations (typically < 10) is small compared to the number of iterations in AGIS (of the order of 100).

A.3 Robustness: detection and downweighting of outliers

The present solution uses an iterative downweighting of observations with large residuals in order to eliminate outliers. The adopted downweighting function corresponds to the well-known Huber loss function (Huber, 1981). This makes a smooth transition from the L_2 (quadratic) norm for small residuals to the robust L_1 (absolute deviation) norm for large residuals – thus combining the best of two worlds: the optimal accuracy of the quadratic norm (i.e., the classical least-squares) for well-behaved observations with nearly Gaussian errors, and the robustness of the L_1 norm (e.g., the median for a single unknown). The downweighting function is (Linde-

Algorithm 1 – Calculating the reduced normal equations and updating the parameters. In the presence of outliers this calculation must be repeated until the weights w have become stable.

- 1: $[\mathbf{F} \mathbf{f}] \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ of size $N_g \times (N_g + 1)$
 - 2: **for all** runs k **do**
 - 3: $[\mathbf{C}_k \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{e}_k] \leftarrow \mathbf{0}$ of size $N_a \times (N_a + N_g + 1)$
 - 4: **for all** stars i observed in the run **do**
 - 5: calculate the local coefficient array \mathbf{p} (of length N_a), the global coefficient array \mathbf{q} (of length N_g), the residual r , and the observation weight w
 - 6: $[\mathbf{C}_k \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{e}_k] \leftarrow [\mathbf{C}_k \mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{e}_k] + \mathbf{p}'[\mathbf{p} \mathbf{q} r] \times w$
 - 7: $[\mathbf{F} \mathbf{f}] \leftarrow [\mathbf{F} \mathbf{f}] + \mathbf{q}'[\mathbf{q} r] \times w$
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: $\mathbf{a}_k = \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} \mathbf{e}_k$ and update the local parameters by \mathbf{a}_k
 - 10: $[\mathbf{F} \mathbf{f}] \leftarrow [\mathbf{F} \mathbf{f}] - \mathbf{D}_k' \mathbf{C}_k^{-1} [\mathbf{D}_k \mathbf{e}_k]$
 - 11: **end for**
 - 12: $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{F}^+ \mathbf{f}$ and update the global parameters by \mathbf{b} (\mathbf{F}^+ is the pseudoinverse of \mathbf{F})
-

gren, GAIA-LL-055)⁴

$$h(z) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |z| < c \\ c(2|z| - c)z^{-2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

with range parameter $c = 3$. Here, z is the normalized residual, i.e., the residual divided by its standard error. When applying this function, it is necessary that the standard errors are realistic, so that (after convergence of the process, i.e., when the outliers have been detected and properly downweighted), most of the residuals follow a distribution consistent with the assigned standard errors. Effectively this means that the normalized residuals z should be approximately Gaussian with unit standard deviation (so that the downweighting sets in beyond $\pm 3\sigma$). The standard errors assigned to the observations are calculated from the Cramér–Rao bound based on the photon and readout noise of the individual CCD samples. With the present test setup it is unavoidable that other error sources (most of them not present in the real Gaia data) will significantly disturb the observations at least for the brighter stars – mechanical vibrations, non-uniform translation of the CCD relative to the mask, thermal variations during the runs, etc. Moreover, the modelling of the LSF and the CTI effects will be far from perfect especially in the initial solutions. As a consequence, the distribution of the residuals will be wider than predicted by the formal standard errors, especially for the brighter stars. If the formal standard errors are used to compute z we will therefore downweight too many of the observations that exceed the 3σ limit just because the σ is too small. In order to avoid this situation the formal standard errors, when used to calculate z , are inflated by the factor $\max(U, 1)$, where U is the

⁴ $h(z)$ was adopted in preference to the alternative ‘exponential decay’ function $d(z)$ (Lindgren, GAIA-LL-055), which tended to give an oscillatory behaviour with the present data: some observations were heavily downweighted in one iteration, and not in the next, etc. The end results were however virtually the same for the two functions.

‘unit weight error’, calculated as the robust RMS normalized residual:

$$U = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{ik} (r_{ik}/\sigma_{ik})^2 \times h_{ik}}{\sum_{ik} h_{ik}}}. \quad (9)$$

where r_{ik} is the residual (in TDI periods), σ_{ik} the formal standard error of the observation, and $h_{ik} = h(z_{ik})$ the downweighting factor. The argument of the Huber function is

$$z_{ik} = \frac{r_{ik}}{\sigma_{ik} \times \max(U, 1)}. \quad (10)$$

Here, $\max(U, 1)$ is used for the inflation factor, rather than U , to avoid a potential instability resulting from a small U leading to the rejection of more observations, which could make U even smaller. (Ideally, $U \simeq 1$ is expected, but U should never be much smaller than 1.) Equations (9) and (10) are of course strongly coupled and the computation of U and the h_{ik} factors must therefore be done as part of the iterations. Thus z_{ik} in the current iteration is using U from the previous iteration. The observation weights used in Algorithm 1 are:

$$w_{ik} = h_{ik} \times \sigma_{ik}^{-2}. \quad (11)$$

Initially, U is set to a large value (100) to accommodate virtually all observations in the first iteration. Typically about 6 iterations are needed for convergence (as determined from the RMS update of the global parameters), but the solution is set to make at most 10 iterations. (A solution in MATLAB using 10 iterations and $\sim 10^7$ observations takes about one hour on a MacBook laptop.)

In Eq. (1) all the unknowns are generally small quantities (of the order of one TDI period or less), except for the attitude phase parameter $a_k^{(0)}$, which is typically several thousand TDI periods. To avoid very large residuals in the first iteration, which could slow down the convergence, an initial robust estimate of the attitude phase is made for every run by computing the median of $u_{ik} - s_j x_i$.

B Appendix: Interpretation of the unexpected ‘star error’

One of the discoveries made during the AGIS-like analysis of the RC#3 data was the existence of an unexpected systematic pattern in the AL residuals, sometimes (e.g., in presentations to the GST and GRTE) referred to as the ‘X factor’ or ‘star error’. This bias is linked to the stars, but has the same sign independent of the mask orientation and can therefore not be explained by an error in the nominal x coordinate of the star on the mask, which would have been absorbed by the parameters $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$. It can however be fully represented by introducing one more parameter $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ per star, as shown by the bracketed term in Eq. (1). Following Lindegren & Crowley (LL-086) we call this augmented equation ‘Model B’ to distinguish it from the original ‘Model A’ without the bracketed term. Each of these is really a whole class of models, which differ in the

number of terms and functional dependencies used to describe the various effects. However, the separation between class A and B models is more important than the subtler differences within each class, because they have quite different characteristics and uses: Model A allows to determine the absolute bias due to the CTI effect, while in Model B part of the CTI bias is absorbed by the additional unknowns $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$. On the other hand, Model B may give a better indication of the residual errors *potentially* achievable in the AGIS-like solution, based on the assumption that the ‘star error’ is caused by deficiencies of the test equipment which will not be present in the real Gaia data. In this section we outline a possible explanation for the ‘star error’ and discuss how it affects the solution.

Theoretically, we expect Model A to describe the geometry of the measurements correctly under certain assumptions. One crucial assumption is that the sky-like pattern on the mask, as described by the nominal coordinates plus $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$, is the same in both mask orientations. The existence of the star error therefore indicates that the mask pattern is slightly different in the two orientations, in a way that cannot be absorbed by a small change in the orientation, scale, and other low-order polynomials described by the attitude and calibration parameters a and c .

There could be many possible explanations for a small change in the star pattern between ‘mask up’ and ‘mask down’. The following appears to be a very plausible explanation, although it may not be the only one. The observed pattern depends both on the mechanical positions of the holes on the mask and, to a smaller degree, on the distortion of the optical imaging from mask to CCD. When the mask is reversed, only the mask itself is rotated 180° , while the optics is unchanged. The observed pattern is therefore in fact different in the two orientations. Consider the following simplified model. As before, let (x, y) be coordinates that are nominally fixed with respect to the mask, and (u, v) corresponding coordinates on the CCD, with u in the AL direction and v in the AC direction. Disregarding offsets and scale differences, the nominal transformation is $(u, v) = (x, y)$ in the ‘mask up’ ($s = +1$) orientation, and $(u, v) = (-x, -y)$ in the ‘mask down’ ($s = -1$) orientation.

Let $f_{\text{mask}}(x, y)$ denote the AL deviation of the mask pattern from the nominal pattern, so that the corresponding shift on the CCD is $\Delta u_{\text{mask}} = s f_{\text{mask}}(x, y)$ depending on the mask orientation s . Similarly, let $\Delta u_{\text{opt}} = f_{\text{opt}}(u, v)$ be the AL deviation due to the optical distortion, which is independent of s and depends on the coordinates (u, v) in the CCD frame. In the two orientations, the total AL shift at mask position (x, y) is:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta u^+(x, y) &= f_{\text{mask}}(x, y) + f_{\text{opt}}(x, y) && \text{(mask up)} \\ \Delta u^-(x, y) &= -f_{\text{mask}}(x, y) + f_{\text{opt}}(-x, -y) && \text{(mask down)} \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (12)$$

When fitting Model B, these shifts are analyzed according to Eq. (1) in terms of the parameters $\Delta x^{(0)}$ and $\Delta x^{(1)}$ (referring to a specific star at coordinates x, y), viz.:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta u^+ &= \Delta x^{(0)} + \Delta x^{(1)} && \text{(mask up)} \\ \Delta u^- &= -\Delta x^{(0)} + \Delta x^{(1)} && \text{(mask down)} \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (13)$$

The result obtained by combining Eqs. (12) and (13) is:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta x^{(0)} &= \frac{1}{2} (\Delta u^+ - \Delta u^-) = f_{\text{mask}}(x, y) + \frac{1}{2} [f_{\text{opt}}(x, y) - f_{\text{opt}}(-x, -y)] \\ \Delta x^{(1)} &= \frac{1}{2} (\Delta u^+ + \Delta u^-) = \frac{1}{2} [f_{\text{opt}}(x, y) + f_{\text{opt}}(-x, -y)] \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (14)$$

Writing the optical distortion separated into its odd and even components, $f_{\text{opt}} = f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{odd}} + f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{even}}$, we have:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta x^{(0)} &= f_{\text{mask}}(x, y) + f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{odd}}(x, y) \\ \Delta x^{(1)} &= f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{even}}(x, y) \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (15)$$

This shows that the *odd* part of the optical distortion is indistinguishable from the mechanical errors of the mask, and therefore show up in the parameters $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$, while the *even* part of the distortion produces the ‘star errors’ in the form on non-zero parameters $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$.

It is useful to examine more carefully what ‘odd’ and ‘even’ distortion means in this context. Consider for example optical distortion that is circularly symmetric around the optical axis, assumed to be at the origin $(u, v) = (0, 0)$. Such distortion is completely described by some function $h(r^2)$ such that $\Delta u = uh(r^2)$ and $\Delta v = vh(r^2)$ with $r^2 = u^2 + v^2$. Then $f_{\text{opt}}(u, v) = uh(r^2)$ and

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{even}}(u, v) &= \frac{1}{2} [f_{\text{opt}}(u, v) + f_{\text{opt}}(-u, -v)] = 0 \\ f_{\text{opt}}^{\text{odd}}(u, v) &= \frac{1}{2} [f_{\text{opt}}(u, v) - f_{\text{opt}}(-u, -v)] = uh(r^2) \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (16)$$

The circularly symmetric distortion turns out to be a purely odd function, and therefore indistinguishable from the mask errors. This makes sense, as the distortion would be the same if the optics had been rotated with the mask. We can therefore conclude that only the non-circularly symmetric part of the optical distortion can possibly produce the ‘star errors’. If the mask is rotated around a point that does not coincide with the optical axis, such errors can be produced even in a circularly symmetric optical system.

Finally it can be noted from Eq. (15) that $\Delta x^{(1)}$ should be an even function. If the star errors are represented by a polynomial in x and y , only terms $x^\alpha y^\beta$ of even degree $\alpha + \beta$ should be present. Geometrically, it means that the pattern is invariant to a rotation by 180° . The pattern actually seen in solution B-5 (shown by the middle right map in Fig. 14) does not exactly have this symmetry, but since the positive values are mainly found in the first and third quadrants, and negative values in the second and fourth, it does show some of the expected pattern.

C Appendix: Further comparison of solutions A-5 and B-5

In subsequent figures various diagrams for the two solutions A-5 and B-5 are compared side by side. On the whole, the solutions are very similar, with a few notable exceptions not further discussed here.

FIGURE 14: Star parameters and related residuals as function of coordinates (x, y) on the mask for solution A-5 (left) and B-5 (right). Plotted are the AL position corrections $\Delta x_i^{(0)}$ (top), the ‘star errors’ $\Delta x_i^{(1)}$ (middle), and the mean AL residuals (bottom).

FIGURE 15: Attitude parameters as function of run index (k) for solution A-5 (left) and B-5 (right). The parameters plotted are the AL shift $a_k^{(00)}$ (top), AL scale error $a_k^{(10)}$ (middle), and rotation $a_k^{(01)}$ (bottom). Magnified sections of the lower left diagrams are displayed in Figs. 4 and 5.

FIGURE 16: Large-scale calibration parameters of degree $\alpha + \beta = 2$ as function of dataset index (j) for solution A-5 (left) and B-5 (right). The parameters plotted are $c_j^{(20)}$ (top), $c_j^{(11)}$ (middle), and $c_j^{(02)}$ (bottom). Error bars show the formal standard errors.

FIGURE 17: Large-scale calibration parameters of degree $\alpha + \beta = 3$ as function of dataset index (j) for solution A-5 (left) and B-5 (right). The parameters plotted are $c_j^{(30)}$ (top), $c_j^{(21)}$ (middle), and $c_j^{(12)}$ (bottom). Error bars show the formal standard errors.

FIGURE 18: Top: Large-scale calibration parameter $c_j^{(03)}$ as function of dataset index (j) for solution A-5 (left) and B-5 (right). Middle: Mean residual per star as function of G , for undamaged (blue) and damaged data (red). Bottom: RMS residual per star as function of G , for undamaged (blue) and damaged data (red). The solid curve in the bottom diagrams is the $\sigma(G)$ relation in AF according to de Bruijne (JDB-053).

FIGURE 19: Top: Formal standard errors σ_{ik} from the LSF fitting as function of G , for undamaged (blue) and damaged data (red). The solid curve is the $\sigma(G)$ relation in AF according to de Bruijne (JDB-053). Bottom: Unit Weight Error (U) per star as function of G , for undamaged (blue) and damaged data (red).

Solution A-5

Solution B-5

FIGURE 20: Top: Mean residual as function of CCD column number m . Middle: Fitted stitching error plus mean residual as function of column number m . Bottom: Unit Weight Error (U) as function of column number m . The vertical red lines mark the boundaries of the stitching blocks. Blue and red points are for undamaged and damaged data, respectively.

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